
The Influence of Peer Relation on the Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students

Shyamolima Moran

Independent Researcher, Email: shyamolimamoran@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17129515>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 24-08-2025

Published: 10-09-2025

Keywords:

Peer mentoring,
Collaborative academic
activities, Awareness
programs

ABSTRACT

College life is not only shaped by books and lectures but also by the invisible ties that bind students together. This study explores how peer relations act as silent architects of undergraduate students of Handique Girls College, Guwahati. Using a descriptive survey method and data were collected from 30 undergraduate students through a self-structured questionnaire. The objective were to examine types of peer relation along with the impact on classroom activities and their role in examination preparation. The findings reveal that most students maintain supportive peer relations and frequently exchange academic information which help them to discuss study related topics beyond the classroom. Peer influence was found to enhance classroom participation, motivation and collaborative learning with group study improved the exam preparation and performance of students. However challenges such as peer conflict and overdependence on friends were observed among a minority of students. The study concludes that positive peer interactions significantly contribute to academic success by fostering motivation, emotional support and effective learning strategies. It recommends peer mentoring, collaborative academic activities and awareness programs to promote constructive peer relations in higher education institutions.

Introduction

The influence of peer relation on the academic performance of undergraduate students holds significance in the educational field. As individual progress through their academic journey, their interactions with peer become increasingly influential in shaping their socio-emotional development, cognitive growth and overall development of educational experience. While numerous factors contribute to academic achievement, peer relationships play a significant role in shaping students learning experience, motivation and overall performance. Among undergraduate students, peer influence can manifest in various ways including collaborative learning, social support, competition and even distraction. The undergraduate years are a critical period of personal and academic development where students not only gain subject knowledge but also form meaningful social connection. For the undergraduate students, the transition from school to college or university often comes with increased social exposure and a shift toward greater autonomy. During this time, peer groups become significant social agents that can influence students attitudes, behaviors and academic engagement. For the undergraduate students, the transition from school to college or university often comes with increased social exposure and a shift toward greater autonomy. During this time, peer groups become significant social agents that can influence students attitudes, behaviors and academic engagement.

Peer relation refers to the social interaction and connections that individual have with their peers or classmate. It is a mutual assistance and collaborative relationship formed during communication and interactions between people of the same or similar age, status or background within educational settings. These relationships are characterized by mutual influence, shared experience and often a sense of equality and mutual understanding. Peer relationships play a vital role in shaping individuals social, emotional and cognitive development particularly during childhood and adolescence. Kram and Isabella (1985) identified three types of peer relationship. They are:

- i) Information peers
- ii) Collegial peers
- iii) Special peers

In Information peer relationship, the individual usually exchange information about work and their organization. This relationship has a low level of self-disclosure and trust. They involved limited personal disclosure and exist mainly for the exchange of work or study related information. Collegial peer relationship are moderate level peer connections that involve mutual trust, shared interests and emotional support beyond just task-related interactions. It has moderate level of trust and self-disclosure

,they often talk about evolving professional roles and job performance. Special peer relationship are the deepest form of peer connection which are marked by high levels of trust, emotional intimacy, mutual support and involved parties are willing to self-disclosure support each other.

This study seeks to examine the extent to which peer relationships influence undergraduate academic performance. It gives importance on types of peer relation among the students of undergraduate because they are at this stage where they spend most of the time with peers and maintain a very close relation with them. At this stage, they imitate each other and observed their behavior . This study also find out the impact of peer relation in classroom activities, it will explore factors such as peer support, peer pressure, group learning and social distractions to determine their impact on students educational outcome. The growing influence of the importance of peer relations, there is a need for more research on the specific ways in which peer relation influence academic performance. The findings of this research will be value able for educators, administrators and students alike offering insights that can inform strategies to foster a more supportive and academically enriching peer environment.

Materials and Methods

For carrying the present study, the investigation undertook Descriptive Survey Method. This method was used to collect data from participation in order to understand the peer relation, conditions and behaviors.

Population and Sample

In the current study, all students of Handique Girl's College was taken as population. The total population was 2900. A total of 30 students were chosen as the sample to fulfil the study's objectives. One of the non-probability sampling methods i.e Random Sampling method was applied using available data believed to reflect the characteristics of the entire population. In the study, data were collected from the sample by the researcher through self structured questionnaire based on the some previous similar studies and multiple questions were used.

After collecting the necessary data, the result was shown with statistical analysis which included proper graph and tables that provided detailed information.

Result

In the present study, data were collected by using a self structured questionnaire on the basis of three objectives i.e study the types of peer relation, find out the impact of peer relation on classroom activities

and investigate the impact of peer relation on students preparation for examination. The responses were analyzed and presented as frequencies and percentage which shown graphically.

Table 1 (To Study the types of peer relation)

S NO	QUESTION	RESPONSE		PERCENTAGE	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
1	Do you feel comfortable talking to most students in your classroom?	18	12	60%	40%
2	Do you feel like you can share personal experience with you friend ?	18	12	60%	40%
3	Do your friends support and help when you face problem?	28	2	93%	7%
4	Do you make new friends easily?	14	16	47%	53%
5	Do your friends frequently exchange academic information with you?	24	6	80%	20%
6	Do your peer group discuss school related topics outside the school?	29	1	97%	3%
7	Have you ever faced challenges in maintaining collegial peer relationship?	7	23	23%	77%

Figure 1:

As seen as table 1, majority of the students responded positively to all the items. The highest ‘Yes’ response were recorded in Question no.6 that peer group discuss study related topic outside the college. Secondly for the friends help and support them when they face any problem and they never faced any challenges while maintaining while collegial peer relationship. Overall it shows a certain influence of peer relation on the academic performance of undergraduate students.

Table 2 (To find out the impact of peer relation on classroom activities)

SI NO	QUESTION	RESPONSE		PERCENTAGE	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
8	Does online communication like group chats, emails strengthens your peer relationship?	23	7	77%	23%
9	Have you ever faced challenged in balancing your special peer relationship and academic	4	26	13%	87%
10	Do your friends influence your academic choices? (eg: course selection, extra curricular activities?)	14	16	47%	53%
11	Do you feel like conflict distract you from your academic work?	2	28	7%	93%
12	Do your friends provide emotional support encouragement?	29	1	97%	3%
13	Do you feel comfortable working in groups with your classmate?	23	7	77%	23%
14	Do you feel your friends encourage you to participate in classroom activities?	28	2	93%	7%

Figure 2

Table 2 shows the impact of peer relation on the classroom activities of students where majority of the students responded positively in all the items. The highest ‘Yes’ response were recorded in question no 12 which state their friends provide emotional support. Secondly in Question no 11 and 14, the students agree that peer conflict doesn’t distract from their study and their friends encouraged to participate in classroom activities.

Table 3 (To investigate the impact of peer relation on students preparation for examination)

SL NO.	Questions	Response		Percentage	
		YES	NO	YES	NO
15	When studying in a group do you feel more motivated to prepare for exams?	23	7	77%	23%
16	Do you think studying with peers improve your exam performances?	25	5	83%	17%
17	Have you ever relied too much on friends instead of preparing your exam?	2	28	7%	93%
18	Do your friends help you to reduce your exam stress before an exam?	13	17	43%	57%
19	Do you feel motivated to study when your friends performs well in exams?	29	1	97%	3%

20	Do you have a close and special friend whom you can trust blindly?	15	15	50%	50%
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Figure 3

Table 3 shows the definite influence of peer relation on the academic performance of students where majority of the students positively respond in all the items. The highest ‘Yes’ response were recorded in Question no 19 which states that the students feel motivated to study when their friends perform well in exam. It has been also found that most of the students accept that studying with peer improve their performance in exam and they prepare themselves instead of relied on friends.

Discussion

The present study investigated the influence of peer relations on the academic performance of undergraduate students with a focus on their role in classroom activities, examination preparation and overall social-emotional support. The findings indicate that peer relationships bring a significant and multifaceted impact both positive and negative on academic outcomes. As seen in table no 1, 93% of the students agreed that their friends help and support them whenever they needed. 80% of the students also agreed that the students frequently exchange academic information with their friends. In table no 2, 97%

of the students response 'Yes' that the friends provide emotional support encouragement to their peers. 93% of the students accept that the friends encourage them to participate in classroom activities. In table no 3, 97% of the students agreed that they feel motivated to study when their friends performs well in exam. 93% of the students accept that they never relied too much on friends instead of preparing their exam.

The result reveal that group study and collaborative peer learning positively influence in exam preparation that studying with peers enhances their performances. In the context of classroom activities, the findings indicate that peer influence strongly encourages participation, collaboration and comfort in group work. This is crucial in undergraduate education, where social exposure and autonomy increase as peers often become primary social agents. Digital communication tools such as group chats and online discussions were also found to reinforce peer bond which reflects hoe students today often learn and connect with each other through technology. In the present study, most of the students accept that their friends exchange academic information with them. They discuss study topics even outside the college and give emotional support when needed. The students feel motivated to study when their friends perform well in exam. Supportive friendship give students confidence and make active in their learning. The study also found that group study is very effective . Majority of the students agreed that studying with peers improves exam performance while only few of the students accept that their friends help to reduce exam stress. This means that while friends can motivate them to study, they cannot always remove the pressure of exams.

Overall the findings prove that peers are an essential part of a students academic journey. Good peer relations improve motivation, confidence, exam preparation and class participation. Since this study was limited to 30 students from Handique Girl's College, more research with larger groups is needed to get a clearer picture. The educational institutions should encourages positive peer interactions through group study, mentoring programs, seminars and counseling programs. This will help students build strong academic habits, manage stress better and succeed both in their studies and personal growth.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlight that peer relation play a crucial role in academic performance of students. By understanding the influence of peer relations, the educators and educational institution design better support system such as peer mentoring programs, academic events, collaborative learning spaces, group activity etc for the development of academic and social programs that encourage constructive peer interactions. Counselor should play prominent and leading role in the matter by

organizing lectures, seminars, career talk that can create positive awareness on the influence of peer on the academic performance of undergraduate students. Thus, it is essential for students to choose their peer circles wisely and for institutions to create frameworks that guide students toward forming healthy and productive peer relationships. By doing so, the student not only enhance individual academic performance but also contribute to a more connected, motivated and successful student community. Therefore, it is essential to understand the nature and quality of peer relationship for fostering academic success among undergraduate. Ultimately, nurturing healthy peer relationships is not only beneficial for academic performance but also crucial for students personal growth and overall well-being during their undergraduate journey and helps the students transition into adulthood and professional life.

Acknowledgements

The author gratefully acknowledges the valuable contributions of all those who supported the successful completion of this research. The author is specially thankful to the participating College (Handique Girl's College, Guwahati, Assam) principal, vice principal and students who generously shared their ideas and viewpoints.

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